

FACTORS INFLUENCING LEARNING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE AMONG BACHELOR OF ARTS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE STUDIES STUDENTS AT MINDANAO STATE UNIVERSITY – SULU

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ABSTRACT

The study is a descriptive research which deals with the factors influencing learning English as second language among Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies Students at Mindanao State University – Sulu. It also deals with the demographic profiles of the respondents in terms of gender, age, and year level. It also deals on the extent of the factors influencing learning English as a second language among Bachelor of Arts in English language studies students at Mindanao State University – Sulu in the context of teacher's influence, personal attitudes influence, and classroom conditions influence. It also deals with the significant difference in the extent of the factors influencing learning English as a second language among Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies students at Mindanao State University – Sulu when data are grouped according to demographic profile in terms of gender, age, and year level, and the significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of the factors influencing learning English as a second language among Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies students at Mindanao State University – Sulu in the context of teacher's influence, personal attitudes influence, and classroom conditions influence. Purposive sampling procedure was employed in selecting the respondents of the study. The research instrument is composed of two parts. Part I is about the demographic profile of the respondents which includes their gender, age, and year level. Part II is composed of 7 statements each on teacher's influence, personal attitudes influence, and classroom conditions influence. There are 5 levels to choose from which ranges from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree". It was found out that the majority of responders were first-

year BAELS students, who are primarily female and the appropriate age for their current year level. The teacher's greatly influenced learning English as second language while personal attitudes and classroom conditions influenced the students to some extent only. There is no significant difference in terms of demographic profile except in terms of age. There is a high to moderate correlation among the three factors.

Keywords: *English Language Learning, Teachers Influence, Personal Attitudes Influences, Classroom Influence, Descriptive research.*

INTRODUCTION

English is now widely used worldwide and has established itself as an international language in many spheres of life. As a result, individuals of all ages and ethnicities have been studying English for a variety of purposes, including socializing, studying overseas, finding employment, and entertaining. But while some people pick up English quickly, others find it difficult to grasp the so-called lingua franca. Some pupils pick up new languages more rapidly and effortlessly than others. Everyone who has studied a second language for themselves or who has instructed others in the use of their second language at school is aware of this basic truth. It is obvious that some language learners succeed only because of their unwavering perseverance, hard work, and determination.

For over two millennia, the topic of language learning has been present on the globe. Currently, approaches and resources are evolving in an effort to find a universal or successful approach to teaching English. These studies have been referred to as those of linguists, psychologists, and educators, who have produced a high level of methodological growth concurrently with technical advancements (Segura, 2012; Thanasoulas, 2015). Developments, which now play a significant part in dynamic teaching and learning, and they set the global standard for English language instruction.

In 2018, Masanori Matsumoto started a study titled "Australian English Language Learners' Perceptions of Their Learning Environment and Factors Affecting Their Motivation." This is a pilot case study on second-language (L2) English learners at a Japanese university. Three students agreed to report on a weekly basis how their motivation changed during a four-week English course provided by an Australian language institute. At the start and finish of the course, they were also asked two questions. The results show that while exposure to a novel learning environment might help students develop their "L2 Selves," the same outside-of-class circumstances can either positively or negatively affect their motivation. Furthermore, throughout the trial, there is no discernible change in the level of motivation. Because the study's participants want to improve their English language skills, it explores how the main differences between English curriculums in Australia and Japan actually affect their actual learning experiences. It's possible, though, that there is more nuance than we realize in the relationship between their motivational intensity and how they perceive contextual circumstances that have influenced their past learning experiences. There can be a

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discrepancy between how learners generally perceive motivational elements and how they affect both the growth and decline of drive to learn.

In 2020, Addisu Sewbihon Getie carried out research on the topic of "Factors affecting students' attitudes towards learning English as a foreign language." In Debre Markos Comprehensive Secondary School in Debre Markos town, Ethiopia, grade 10 English language learners' attitudes were investigated in this study in an effort to identify the elements impacting those attitudes. From a total of 1030 students, the researcher chose 103 sample students (10%) at random for the study. A well-considered and comprehensive questionnaire was created in order to collect data. Nine sample students were chosen specifically for a focus group discussion, and English teachers instructing Grade 10 were also chosen for an interview. The information was then examined both quantitatively and qualitatively. The study's major conclusions demonstrated that grade 10 pupils had good attitudes on learning EFL. Parents of students, native English speakers, and peer groups are examples of positive social influences on students' opinions. Nonetheless, the physical learning environment, seating arrangements, and classroom design, in addition to the English language teachers, all negatively impacted the students' attitudes. However, the results demonstrated that target language learners had favorable feelings toward the second element of the learning environment—the grade 10 English textbook. This demonstrates how the study's environment, which uses resources for teaching English to non-native speakers, positively affects students' perceptions. Therefore, reducing the target language learners' psychological variables—that is, their emotional filters—can aid in their language learning. The study's findings suggest that the actual physical learning environment has to be enhanced. To do this, the government ought to collaborate with educators, students, and the general public.

The way that teachers approach teaching second languages in the classroom might affect how well their students do. Wong (2007) asserts that there is a direct and substantial correlation between a student's proficiency in English and their teacher. While some teachers may result in subpar performance and non-directive behavior, others might inspire pupils to learn and exhibit positive behavior. The educational strategies and tactics used by educators have an impact on children's views as well. It has been discovered that many traditional language-teaching techniques are ineffective (Lightbown & Spada, 2013). Explicit instruction appears to keep students from identifying crucial inputs in subjects like phonology, grammar, and vocabulary. Furthermore, Burns (1982) found that teachers who prioritize student-centered methods create a classroom that is more dynamic and interesting than teachers who adhere to traditional methods.

Owing to the principles of learning mentioned above, this study will determine the extent of factors influencing learning English as a second language during School Year 2021-2022. The purpose of this study is to collect empirical data that will provide the foundation for a description of the current state of English language learning.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the extent of factors influencing learning English as a second language among Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies (BA ELS) students at Mindanao State University-Sulu (MSU) in during the School Year 2023-2024.

Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the students-respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Gender
 - 1.2 Age; and
 - 1.3 Year Level?
2. What is the extent of the factors influencing learning English as a second language among BA ELS students at Mindanao State University-Sulu, in terms of:
 - 2.1 Teacher's Influence;
 - 2.2 Personal Attitudes influence; and
 - 2.3 Classroom conditions Influence?
3. Is there a significant difference in the factors influencing learning English as a second language among BA ELS students at Mindanao State University-Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of;
 - 3.1 Gender;
 - 3.2 Age; and
 - 3.3 Year Level?
4. Is there a significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of factors influencing learning English as a second language among BA ELS students at MSU-Sulu?

METHODOLOGY

Research design

A descriptive research design was used in this study. This study aims to characterize, measure, and infer in addition to finding correlations between variables and enabling the forecasting of future occurrences based on current knowledge or phenomena observed by BA ELS students. These problem include: The socio-demographic profile of the students-respondents in terms of; Gender, Age and Year Level. Also, the extent of the factors influencing learning English as a second language among BA ELS students at Mindanao State University-Sulu, in terms of; Teacher's Influence, Personal Attitudes influence and Classroom Conditions Influence.

Furthermore, the significant difference in the extent of factors influencing learning English as a second language among BA ELS students at Mindanao State University-Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of; Gender,

Age and Year Level. At the same time, the significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of factors influencing learning English as a second language among BA ELS students at MSU-Sulu.

The primary source of the quantitative data used in this study to address the research questions was the BA ELS students of Mindanao State University-Sulu. The information used to strengthen the theoretical and conceptual frameworks of this study came from online research. Questionnaires was used to get information from the respondents.

Research locale

During the school year 2023–2024, a survey was carried out among BA ELS students of Mindanao State University-Sulu. The said institution is one from the most populated university in the Province of Sulu.

Respondents of the study

The BA ELS students of Mindanao State University-Sulu during the 2023–2024 school year were the study's respondents. The purpose of the study was to find out what the respondents think about the Factors influencing learning English as a second language. The respondents listed below have been categorized based on their areas of academic expertise.

Mindanao State University-Sulu			
Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies			
Year Level	Section	Population	Frequency
First year	3	147	35
Second year	2	93	25
Third year	2	78	25
Fourth year	1	17	15
Total			100

Sampling design

In this study, a purposive sampling procedure was used in conjunction with a non-probability sample design. From at least four (4) section of BA ELS students, a total of one hundred (100) representative samples were utilized. This study's use of the purposive sampling technique guaranteed that the BA ELS students included as study samples are well represented in terms of gender, age, and year level.

Research instrument

A survey questionnaire was the instruments in this study in gathering the data on demographic profile and extent of the factors influencing learning English as a second language among BA ELS students in Mindanao State University-Sulu.

The primary tool used to collect information on the state of the factors influencing learning English as a second language among BAELS students of Mindanao State University-Sulu was the survey questionnaire. There were two parts of the research instruments that were used in this study. First, part of the questionnaire focused on obtaining the demographic profile of the respondents which includes gender, age, and year level. And, the second part focused on the collection of data on the extent of the factors influencing learning English as a second language, will be contained to the three components based on the study of Febti Mahani Batubara, Tatum Derin, Nunung Susilo Putri, & Ratih Saltri Yudar (2020) Five Factors Influencing the Students' Motivation to Learn English as a Foreign Language. It consists of the following dimensions: Teacher's Influence, Personal Attitudes Influence and Classroom Condition Influence.

Under the three (3) Categories namely, the teacher's influence, Personal Attitudes influence and Classroom condition influence were contained seven (7) items each. Each items in all these categories were answered through 5-points Likert scales such as 5=Strongly Agree, 4=Agree, 3=Undecided, 2=Disagree, 1=Strongly Disagree.

Data gathering procedure

In the collection of the data, the following steps were employed:

1) A permit to administer the questionnaire was sought from the Dean of the Graduate Studies of the Sulu State College and then from the Chancellor of Mindanao State University-Sulu, and then from the Dean of the College of Arts and Sciences and lastly from the Chairperson of the Department of Languages.

2) The researcher launched, administered, and retrieved the questionnaire personally.

Statistical treatment of data

The following descriptive statistical technique were correctly used to handle the data collected for this study:

1. For the research problem number one (1), Frequency and percentages were used to ascertain the BAELS students' profile.
2. For the research problem number two (2), The degree of the factors influencing Mindanao State University-Sulu BAELS students' acquisition of English as a second language during the school year 2023–2024 were determined using mean and standard deviation.
3. For research problem number three (3), when data are grouped according to gender, the t-test for independent samples were used to determine the significant differences in the extent of the factors influencing learning English as a second language among BAELS students of Mindanao State University-Sulu during Year 2023–2024; when data are grouped according to age and Year Level, One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to determine the significant differences.
4. For the research problem number two (2), The degree of correlation between the sub-categories covered by the Extent of the factors influencing learning English as a second language among BAELS students of Mindanao State University-Sulu during the School Year 2023–2024 was determined using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson's r).

RESULTS

1. ***What is the demographic profile of the Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies students at Mindanao State University - Sulu in terms of 1.1 gender, 1.2 age, and 1.3 year level?***

1.1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Gender

Table 1.1 presents the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of gender.

Sixty – nine or 68.3% of the respondents are females and only 32 or 31.7% are males.

Table 1.1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	32	31.7%
Female	69	68.3%

TOTAL	101	100%
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1.2 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Table 1.2 presents the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age. It showed that 66 or 65.3% are between 19 – 24 years old and only 5 or 5% are between 29 – 35 years old.

Table 1.2 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18 years old and below	20	19.8%
19 – 24 years old	66	65.3%
25 – 28 years old	10	9.9%
29 – 35 years old	5	5.0%
TOTAL	101	100%

1.3 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Year Level

As gleaned from table 1.3 the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of year level. It showed that 35 or 34.7% of the respondents are first year college students while only 17 or 15.2% are fourth year college students.

Table 1.3 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Year Level

Year Level	Frequency	Percentage
First Year	35	34.7%
Second Year	24	23.8%
Third Year	25	25.3%
Fourth Year	17	15.2%
TOTAL	101	100%

2. What is the extent of the factors influencing learning English as a second language among Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies students at Mindanao State University – Sulu in the context of 2.1 teacher’s influence, 2.2 personal attitudes influence, and 2.3 classroom conditions influence?

Table 2.1 provide the result of the factors influencing learning English as a second language among Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies students at Mindanao State University - Sulu in the context of teacher’s influence.

It showed that the respondents either **agree** or **disagree** on the different statements. Among those they indicated **agree** are; my teacher seldom gives me the chance to express my thoughts or feelings during the lesson (mean = 4.380, SD = 1.180) and I listen attentively when the teacher presents the material (mean = 4.263, SD = 1.046). For **disagree**, the statements are; I’m bored when the teacher presents the material (mean = 1.940, SD = 1.023); and I feel lazy to listen when my teacher speaks in English (mean = 1.720, SD =1.074). The average mean of 3.500 means that the BAELS students **agree** on the extent of teacher’s influence in learning English as a second language.

Table 2.1 Extent of the Factors Influencing Learning English as a Second Language among Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies Students in the Context of Teacher’s Influence

Teacher’s Influence	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. My teacher seldom gives me the chance to express my thoughts or feelings during the lesson.	4.380	1.108	Agree
2. I listen attentively when the teacher presents the material.	4.263	1.046	Agree
3. I’m bored when the teacher presents the material.	1.940	1.023	Disagree
4. My teacher encourages me to speak in English every time.	4.130	.734	Agree
5. I am active when the teacher ask me to participate in the class.	3.788	.786	Agree
6. My teacher always gives me a chance to express my thoughts during class.	4.260	.799	Agree

7. I feel lazy to listen when my teacher speaks in English.	1.720	1.074	Disagree
AVERAGE	3.500		AGREE

LEGEND

SCALE	RANGE	INTERPRETATION
5	4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.50 – 4.49	Agree
3	2.50 – 3.49	Undecided
2	1.50 – 2.49	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree

Table 2.2 reveals the factors influencing learning English as a second language among Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies students at Mindanao State University – Sulu in the context of personal attitudes influence.

The respondents indicated **undecided** in almost all statements and among those are; I'm nervous to speak English in school (mean = 2.700, SD = 1.314); I think English is difficult (mean = 2.810, SD = .849); and I often give up when I cannot finish my assignment (mean = 2.909, SD = 1.773). However, they also indicated **agree** in statement 6 which is on; I always try to finish the assignment independently (mean = 4.070, SD = .977); and **disagree** on statement 5 which is on; I prefer to talk with my friends than listening to the teacher during lessons (mean = 2.330, SD = 1.505). The average mean of 3.010 means that BAELS students **cannot decide** whether personal attitudes can influence or not learning English as a second language.

Table 2.2 Extent of the Factors Influencing Learning English as a Second Language among Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies Students in the Context of Personal Attitudes Influence

Personal Attitudes Influence	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I think English is difficult.	2.810	.849	Undecided
2. I always speak English with my teacher and friends.	2.960	.828	Undecided
3. I'm nervous to speak English in school.	2.700	1.314	Undecided
4. I prefer to speak English in school.	3.290	.977	Undecided
5. I prefer to talk with my friends than listening to the teacher during lessons.	2.330	1.505	Disagree

6. I always try to finish the assignment independently.	4.070	.977	Agree
7. I often give up when I cannot finish my assignment.	2.909	1.773	Undecided
AVERAGE	3.010		UNDECIDED

LEGEND

SCALE	RANGE	INTERPRETATION
5	4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.50 – 4.49	Agree
3	2.50 – 3.49	Undecided
2	1.50 – 2.49	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree

Table 2.3 exposes the extent of the factors influencing learning English as a second language among BAELS students at MSU – Sulu.

The respondents indicated *undecided* in almost all statements except in statement 6 where they indicated *agree* and that is on; I learn well in the class that is silent (mean = 3.500, SD = 1.374). For *undecided*, some of the statements are; I feel bored in the class that is silent (mean = 2.727, SD = 1.398); I enjoy the class that is noisy and messy (mean = 2.790, SD = 1.565); and a noisy class encourage me to express my thoughts or feelings in the English lesson (mean = 2.800, SD = 1.128). The average mean of 2.644 means that the BAELS students are *undecided* on the influence of classroom conditions in learning English as a second language.

Table 2.3 Extent of the Factors Influencing English Learning as a Second Language among Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies Students in the Context of Classroom Conditions Influence

Classroom Condition Influence	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I enjoy in the class that is hot and dirty.	2.920	1.710	Undecided
2. A silent class stimulates me to express my thoughts or feeling in English lesson.	3.250	1.242	Undecided
3. I feel bored in the class that is silent.	2.727	1.398	Undecided
4. I enjoy the class that is noisy and messy.	2.790	1.565	Undecided

5. A noisy class encourage me to express my thoughts or feelings in the English lesson.	2.800	1.128	Undecided
6. I learn well in the class that is silent.	3.500	1.374	Agree
7. I feel lazy in the class that is messy and noisy.	3.310	1.339	Undecided
AVERAGE	2.644		UNDECIDED

LEGEND

SCALE	RANGE	INTERPRETATION
5	4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.50 – 4.49	Agree
3	2.50 – 3.49	Undecided
2	1.50 – 2.49	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree

3. *Is there a significant difference in the extent of the factors influencing learning English as a second language among Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies students – Sulu when data are grouped according to gender, age, and year?*

The t-test was used for gender since there are only two categories. The sig. value of 0.365 for teacher’s influence is greater than the p – value of .05, the sig. value of 0.710 for personal attitude influence is greater than the p – value at .05, and the sig. value of 0.425 for classroom condition influence is also greater than the p – value of .05. It means that the null hypothesis is accepted.

There is no significant difference in the extent of the factors influencing learning English as a second language among BAELS students of Mindanao State University-Sulu when data are grouped according to their gender.

Table 3.1 t – test for Significant Difference in the Extent of the Factors Influencing Learning English as a Second Language among BAELS Students at Mindanao State University – Sulu in terms of Gender

Variables	Grouping	Mean		Diff.	t	Sig.	Description
		Mean	SD				
Teacher’s	Male	3.200	.630				Not

Influence	Female	3.630	.750	0.43	16.390	.365	Significant
Personal Attitude	Male	3.650	.550				Not
Influence	Female	4.380	.720	0.73	18.250	.710	Significant
Classroom Condition	Male	4.210	.810				Not
Influence	Female	4.650	.790	0.44	15.450	.425	Significant

Significant at .05 level

In Table 3.2 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used for age and year level. The sig. value of 0.869 for age is greater than the p - value of .05 and the sig. value of the 0.272 for year level is greater than the p-value at .05. It could only mean that the null hypothesis is accepted in terms of age and year level.

There is no significant difference in the extent of the factors influencing learning English as a second language among BAELS students when data are grouped according to their age and year level.

Table 3.2 ANOVA for Significant Difference in the Extent of the Factors Influencing Learning English as a Second Language among BAELS Students at Mindanao State University - Sulu in terms of Age and Year Level

		Sum of		Mean			Interpretation
		Square	df	Square	f	Sig.	
AGE							Not
	Between	.902	3	0.301	0.242	.869	Significant
Groups		120.658	97	1.243			
	Within Groups	121.560	100				
	Total						
Year Level							Not
	Between	4.865	3	1.622	1.330	.272	Significant
Groups		116.550	97	1.202			
	Within Groups	121.414	100				
	Total						

Significant at .05 level

4. Is there a significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of the factors influencing learning English as a second language among BAELS students, Mindanao State University – Sulu in the context of teacher’s influence, personal attitudes influence, and classroom conditions influence?

Pearson Product – Moment Correlation or Pearson r was used to determine if there is a significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of the factors influencing learning English as a second language among BAELS students at MSU – Sulu in the context of teacher’s influence, personal attitudes influence, and classroom conditions influence.

The average value of $r = 0.605$ for teacher’s influence was interpreted as **high correlation** while the average value of $r = 0.449$ for personal attitudes influence was interpreted as **moderate correlation** at significant value of .05 two- tailed test, and the average value of .463 for classroom conditions influence was also interpreted as **moderate correlation**

Table 4. Significant Correlation in the Extent of the Factors Influencing Learning English as a Second Language among BAELS students at Mindanao State University – Sulu in the Context of Teacher’s Influence, Personal Attitudes Influence, and Classroom Conditions Influence

		Pearson r	Sig.	n	Description
Teacher’s Influence	Personal Attitudes Influence	.564	.000	101	High
	Classroom Conditions Influence	.646	.000	101	High
	AVERAGE	0.605			HIGH
Personal Attitudes	Teacher’s Influence	.548	.000	101	High
	Classroom Conditions Influence				

Influence		.349	.000	101	Moderate
	AVERAGE	0.449			MODERATE
	Teacher's Influence	.529	.000	101	High
Classroom Conditions Influence	Personal Attitudes Influence		.000	101	Moderate
	AVERAGE	0.463			MODERATE

*Correlation Coefficient is significant at $\alpha = .05$

Correlation Scales adapted from Hopkins (2002):

0.0– 0.1 = Nearly Zero; 0.1 – 0.3 = Low; 0.3 – 0.5 = Moderate; 0.5 – 0.7 = High;
0.7 – 0.9 = Very High; 0.9 – 1.0 = Nearly Perfect

DISCUSSION

On the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of gender, age and year level

The findings indicated that barely a third of the respondents were men and that over half of the respondents were women. The most of them are between the ages of 19 and 24, with very few falling between the 29 and 35 age range. Only a small percentage of respondents—roughly one-third—were fourth-year college students, whereas the majority of respondents were first-years.

It implies that BAELS students at MSU - Sulu are dominated by female students, mostly are in the right age for their present year level, and the freshmen students were more than the other students as far as year level is concern.

On the extent of the factors influencing learning English as a second language among BAELS students at Mindanao State University – Sulu in the context of teacher's influence, personal attitudes influence, and classroom conditions influence

BAELS students at MSU – Sulu agree that teacher's influenced their learning English as a second language while they are undecided on personal attitudes influence and classroom conditions influence.

The result implies that BAELS students at MSU – Sulu were sure that teachers greatly influenced their learning English as a second language. However, they are unsure whether personal attitudes influence and classroom conditions influence has something to do with their learning English as a second language.

According to Xuan and Thang's study from 2022, students' perceptions of studying English as a second language might be influenced by unrelated factors. Together with the unique qualities of teachers, such their manner and degree of experience, the factors include instructional materials, topic matter, and course format.

On the significant difference in the extent of the factors influencing learning English as a second language among BAELS students at Mindanao State University – Sulu when data are grouped according to gender, age, and year level

There is no significant difference in the extent of the factors influencing learning English as second language among BAELS students at MSU – Sulu in terms of gender and year level. However, a significant difference was found in terms of age.

The result implies that the different demographic profiles of the BAELS students at MSU - Sulu failed to detect any differences in the extent of the factors that influence their learning English as second language except in terms of age.

The study supports the Affective Filter Hypothesis Model by Stephen Krashen (1985) which suggests that a learner's emotional state, attitudes, and motivations can impact the ability to pick up a new language.

On the significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of the factors influencing learning English as a second language among BAELS students at Mindanao State University – Sulu in the context of teacher's influence, personal attitudes influence, and classroom conditions influence

There is a high correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of the factors influencing learning English as second language among BAELS students at MSU – Sulu in the context of teacher's influence. However, there is a moderate correlation in the context of personal attitudes influence and classroom conditions influence.

The result simply implies that teachers can greatly influence the BAELS students in learning English as a second language more than the personal attitudes influence and classroom conditions influence.

In a study by Castro (2018), the result indicates that the students' sentiments toward their current learning environments and their linguistic dominance are significantly correlated. The students' attitudes toward learning English have a direct impact on how well they rate their English proficiency.

Conclusions

The following was concluded based on the findings of the study:

The BAELS students at MSU – Sulu were mostly females, with a few students who attended college late because their age showed that they are supposed to be graduates already. First year BAELS students comprised the majority among the respondents of the study.

It only showed that teacher's influenced learning English as second language more than the influenced of both personal attitudes and classroom conditions.

The absence of difference in the extent of the factors influencing learning English as second language among BAELS students at MSU – Sulu when data are grouped according to gender and year level only proves that the two variables are not determinants in learning English. However, age proves that it influences learning English.

The ***moderate correlation*** in the extent of the factors influencing learning English as a second language among BAELS students at MSU - Sulu in terms of personal attitudes and classroom conditions prove that the two variables can only influence to some extent. Teachers prove that they can really influence learning English among students.

Recommendations

This study recommends the following:

1. Further study on the extent of the influence of the different factors in learning English among college students must be conducted to really prove their influence on the students learning.
2. Future researchers on the same topic should add variables like parental influence and peer influence not covered by this study.
3. Teachers should constantly encourage learners to speak English in school and avoid feeling ashamed in speaking the language.
4. English teachers should give their best in teaching the subject and should serve as an inspiration and role model for learners to look up to.
5. English teachers should avoid code switching while teaching the subject in class in order to encourage students more to speak the language.

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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The ethical care of all participants—especially the Mindanao State University-Sulu teachers—is given top priority in this study. The researcher constantly sought to protect the respondents' right to privacy while delving into important subjects.

First and foremost, the participants received a comprehensive informed consent form outlining the goals, methods, possible risks and advantages, and confidentiality policies of the study. Additionally, anonymization of every piece of trial data was scrupulously followed in cases when the respondents' specific information was not connected to the same. Regarding participant privacy, data collection took place in a private location, and the collected data were kept in a secure archive that is only accessible by researchers. Similarly, each and every member received respect regardless of their divergent beliefs and viewpoints. In addition, the researchers made an effort to provide the responders with a secure and welcoming environment so they felt free to talk about their experiences.

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